

WAYS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES AT AN EARLY AGE

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Abstract: This article describes the methods of teaching English to children of preschool age, and now English is becoming a world language, so it should be started from preschool, i.e. kindergarten age, the article provides information about this.

Key words: foreign language, words, phonetics, rule, dog, rabbit, rhythmic music, methodology.

After our country gained independence, great attention has been paid to learning foreign languages in our country. In particular, the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the further improvement of the system of learning foreign languages" adopted on December 10, 2012, and the introduction of foreign languages in the first classes of general education schools from the 2013-2014 school year. Nowadays, foreign language, especially English is taught not only to students of schools, lyceums, colleges and universities, but to students of preschool educational institutions and employees working in various fields. There's a reason for that, of course. Learning the languages of economically, scientifically, and culturally developed countries is the main factor in mastering the achievements of world science and development. In the last few years, learning a foreign language has become a necessity rather than a way of self-development. A foreign language has become a mandatory component of education not only in schools and universities, but also in many additional preschool educational institutions. The demand for learning foreign languages in society, on the one hand, as well as parents' understanding that language is not only a factor in the education of a modern person, but also the basis of his social and material well-being in society, on the other hand, early learning of a foreign language especially popular and relevant. If 20 years ago knowledge of a language was required only in certain fields of work, now it is necessary to master at least one.

Language learning also depends on the age periods. According to psychologists, children learn language faster and easier than adults. The main reasons for this are the natural tendency of children to learn languages, the fact that they have a strong ability to imitate, and the fact that children have more time than adults. It should be noted that 6-7-year-old children do not understand the meaning of information, but memorize it mechanically. Therefore, it is necessary not to start teaching English to elementary school students with grammatical concepts.

Otherwise, from the first step of learning a foreign language, it is possible to strain the child and extinguish his interest.

Teaching a foreign language to young children is very difficult and responsible. It is known that children are more comfortable to learn. Until recently, teaching methods were aimed at school-aged children, now parents are trying to start learning a foreign language as early as possible. The main goals of teaching preschool children a foreign language:

- formation of children's basic communication skills in a foreign language;
- the ability to use a foreign language to achieve one's goals, to express one's thoughts and feelings in life communication;
- create a positive attitude to further study of foreign languages;
- arouse interest in the life and culture of other countries.

Preschool age is especially favorable for starting to learn a foreign language. Children of this age are distinguished by their sensitivity to language phenomena, they are interested in understanding their speech experiences, the "secrets" of language. They easily and firmly remember a small amount of language material. With age, these favorable factors lose their power. There is another reason why an early age is better for learning a foreign language. The younger the child, the less challenges. Teaching children is a very difficult issue that requires a completely different methodological approach than schoolchildren and adults. If an adult speaks a foreign language, it does not mean that he can teach others. When faced with methodologically inefficient lessons, children can long-term hate the foreign language and lose confidence in their abilities. Only experienced professionals should work with preschool children. In the preschool age, during the teaching of English, children gradually develop the basics of communicative competence;

- the ability to correctly repeat English words from a phonetic point of view "behind the teacher, mother tongue or speaker, that is, the gradual formation of listening attention, phonetic hearing and correct pronunciation;
- acquisition, integration and activation of English vocabulary;
- mastering a certain number of simple grammatical structures, making a coherent statement.

The methodology of conducting direct educational activities should be built taking into account the age and individual characteristics of the structure of children's language skills and should be directed to their development. Communication in a foreign language should be motivational and directed. It is necessary to create a positive psychological attitude towards a foreign language

in a child, and the way to create such a positive motivation is to play. The game is both a form of organization and a method of conducting lessons in which children gather a certain amount of English vocabulary, learn many poems, songs, count rhymes, etc. This form of conducting lessons creates favorable conditions for mastering language skills and speaking skills. The ability to rely on game activity allows you to give a natural impetus to speech in a foreign language, to make even the simplest phrases interesting and meaningful. Playing in the teaching of a foreign language does not contradict the educational activity, but is organically connected with it.

Cartoons. While learning a foreign language, children do not understand the words in the cartoon, but they try to understand the words they use through the actions of the characters in the cartoon. This is an interesting and effective way for children to learn the language.

Primary school students in rural areas usually grow up far away from the English language environment, and children's thinking remains abstract, and the process of acquiring new knowledge is always based on emotions. Therefore, English teachers of kindergarten age children make full use of materials around students, flashcards, and other learning aids in teaching through easy methods. When teaching words like "banana" and "apple," teachers can simultaneously teach new color words by showing fruits like bananas and apples. Children use classroom objects to organize learning activities and teach them how to use them in a foreign language. Of course, the teachers' methodology plays a big role in the use of materials during teaching. For example, when teaching related words, you first show the child the object and encourage him to say it, the students pronounce the words, and repeat the new word again using the pictures on the cards to reinforce the word they have pronounced. pronounced. In the teaching of words, teachers can determine the content of the text, and in order to attract the attention of students, the educator can draw their picture on the board by pronouncing the words together with them. Therefore, a teacher is required to have drawing skills. This not only reduces the difficulty of teaching, but also helps students to gradually consolidate the knowledge they have learned. In order for students to feel their progress in the process of learning the English language, it is necessary to have a perfect approach to each educational activity. That is the only way children are motivated to learn. Nowadays, nursery school children are more receptive to new knowledge, so the curriculum in kindergartens has been intensified accordingly. Using songs and action games to improve the classroom environment. Creating a flexible classroom atmosphere

is sometimes more important than any teaching method. In the class, at the beginning of the lesson, all the children, led by the teacher, sang a song together with a nice English song and danced a little to its tune. This in itself will help them exercise their bodies, become more energetic and memorize the lyrics of the song faster. The English environment, importantly, allows for a natural entry into a good learning atmosphere. Children's self-control is weak, and it is difficult for them to concentrate and hold their attention during the whole lesson.

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